

Optimizing tunnels modelling through visual programming

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Abstract

This thesis aims to optimise and automate the tunnel modelling in Revit by means of Dynamo. An existing project of the drainage tunnel already designed in CAD and supplemented by a BIM model was taken as a basis. The path of the tunnel as an input was obtained from the Civil 3D.

The first study aimed to optimize the process of modelling of the main concrete structures. Various sections of the tunnel were analyzed in order to create a parametric adaptive component. Several prototypes were created in order to get the component, capable of following a curved path with an absence or a low extent of the overlap between two sequential units depending on the type of the bending: flat or spacious. Placement based on the path with an adjustment of the joints was done by means of Dynamo.

The second study aimed to optimize the process of modelling of the steel supporting ribs with joints. Adaptive component comprised of radial steel ribs was complemented with joint details by means of Dynamo. As well as in the concrete unit, expansion of the external outline was implemented.

The third study aimed to apply a generative design to optimize the displacement of the

injection holes for the grouting to meet the condition of the minimal self-intersection to form a waterproof barrier.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/NrbrNNpfPfc>

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